

Grain quality

Selection for nonchalky grain in two Thai experimental rice lines

Kruawan Attaviriyasook, first grade official, Rice Grain Quality Section, Rice Division, Department of Agriculture, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives; and B. R. Jackson, plant breeder, The Rockefeller Foundation, G.P.O. Box 2453, Bangkok, Thailand

Rice breeders in Thailand are sometimes disappointed in promising experimental lines because they discover, after several cycles of selection, that the milled grain is too chalky to meet the rigid grain-quality standards of the government.

In recent observations, the Thai lines CNT200-1 and BKN6624-257-1 showed unusually wide adaptation, excellent yield, good disease resistance, and acceptable grain length. Such characteristics should have easily qualified the lines for release as recommended government varieties. Unfortunately, their average chalkiness ratings exceeded the 1.5 score, the upper limit imposed by the government. Grain-quality researchers had previously observed wide ranges in chalkiness in seed from the two

Distribution of chalkiness scores for two populations selected from the Thai experimental lines CNT200-1 and BKN6624-257-1, grown under monsoon season conditions. Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, 1976.

lines but assumed that the condition was due to environmental effects.

A study made by Nakatani several years ago suggested that chalkiness might be controlled by several genes interacting with the environment. Since most pedigree lines are bulked in the early generation after hybridization, it was theorized that segregation for chalkiness

might continue under selfing and eventually result in an array of genotypes, some chalky and others nonchalky. To test the hypothesis, nonchalky and chalky grains were randomly selected from a bulk sample of CNT200-1 and BKN6624-257-1 and planted at the Bangkok Rice Experiment Station in the 1976 wet season.

The means of chalkiness scores of the two populations differed by 1.57. The distribution of the low chalkiness population was strikingly different from that of the chalky population. The two populations overlapped primarily because one family in the chalky population had unusually lower scores, averaging 0.60, than the other families, which tended to have average scores higher than 2.0.

BKN6624-257-1 was selected from a cross of IR262 and Niaw Sanpahtawng, a popular glutinous variety in North and Northeastern Thailand. Although the separation of the chalky and nonchalky populations was not as clear as that in CNT200-1, the means and distribution suggest that the selection had at least some effect. The result may be partly due to the effects of the waxy gene from the Niaw Sanpahtawng parent, since many of the milled seeds had an opaque appearance. ❧

Adverse soils

Breeding for resistance to hydrogen sulfide injury in Tamil Nadu, India

K. M. Balasubramaniam, S. Krishnaswami, and V. Subbiah, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India

Subartesian wells irrigate an area of about 4,000 ha in Tamil Nadu. Hydrogen sulfide in the irrigation water of such wells hampers the initial establishment of rice and reduces yields by 40 to 55%. To develop rice varieties that will withstand

this adverse situation, breeding programs were initiated at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu.

Seven segregating populations were tested in a location where the irrigation water has hydrogen sulfide. The progeny of the cross combinations Tiruveni/IR30 and Tiruveni/Co 39 performed well under the adverse condition. Among varieties already released, Tiruveni, IR30, and ADT-9 appear promising. Further work is in progress. ❧

Invitation to authors

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